

POS Moderates The Follower Green Awareness And-Leader Commitment

Tanya Munir, Sajjad Nawaz Khan, Adham Fayad

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Abstract

The study aimed to fulfill its objectives by examining how followers' environmental values influence leaders' commitment to environmentally friendly practices, with perceived organizational support acting as a moderating factor. The research involved gathering data from 282 IT company employees in Pakistan and conducting a quantitative analysis using SEM-PLS. The results of the analysis revealed the significance of all hypotheses. It was found that followers' green values serve as a valuable tool for promoting environmentally sustainable practices within IT companies and also contribute to motivating leaders to embrace such practices. Additionally, perceived organizational support was found to moderate the relationship between followers' green values and leaders' commitment to environmental initiatives. From a practical standpoint, these findings emphasize the importance of recruiting, retaining, and investing in employees who possess strong environmental values, as their influence is crucial in strengthening leaders' commitment to environmentally friendly practices. This perspective on "green followership" plays a vital role in advancing sustainability efforts within organizations. Furthermore, this study contributes to Shamir's (2007) "Reversing the Lens" perspective, highlighting followers' significant role in leadership dynamics. It underscores that followers are equally essential as leaders in promoting effective green leadership. Additionally, the study extends the resource-based theory by suggesting that followers provide valuable resources to leaders, including knowledge, expertise, and support, in the context of environmentally sustainable initiatives.

Introduction

Green practices play a pivotal role in modern industries, contributing to a more sustainable and environmentally responsible approach to production and manufacturing. These practices reduce the environmental footprint of industries by minimizing resource consumption and waste generation. Through strategies like energy-efficient processes, waste reduction, and the use of renewable resources, industries can significantly decrease their negative impact on the environment. This helps protect natural ecosystems and enhances the long-term viability of businesses by reducing operational costs and ensuring compliance with increasingly stringent environmental regulations. Green practices foster innovation and competitiveness in industries (Firdaus, 2014). Embracing sustainable technologies and processes often leads to the development of more efficient and cost-effective solutions. Companies that invest in research and development of green technologies gain a competitive edge in the market. Consumers are becoming increasingly eco-conscious, and businesses that adopt green practices can attract a growing customer base (Min & Galle, 2001). Additionally, adopting these practices can open up new markets and partnerships, as many governments and organizations actively support and reward environmentally responsible businesses.

Promoting green practices in the IT industry is not only an ethical responsibility but also a strategic imperative (Chen & Chang, 2012). Embracing green values can significantly contribute to a more sustainable and environmentally responsible IT sector. Firstly, the IT industry can lead by example in reducing its carbon footprint. Green values within IT companies should prioritize energy-efficient data centers, sustainable supply chain management, and reducing electronic waste through responsible recycling and disposal (Guziana, 2011). Similarly, follower green values can drive innovation in the IT sector. Companies that prioritize sustainability often invest in research and development of eco-friendly technologies, such as low-power hardware, renewable energy solutions, and energy-efficient software. These innovations not only benefit the environment but also lead to cost savings and competitive advantages.

Follower green values encourage a culture of sustainability within the organization (Islam et al., 2020). Followers are more likely to engage in eco-friendly practices both at work and in their personal lives when they see their company prioritizing green values (Kumari, 2012). This can lead to a more environmentally conscious workforce, resulting in reduced energy consumption, paperless offices, and lower transportation emissions as employees may opt for remote work or carpooling. Moreover, embracing follower green values can enhance the

company's reputation and attract environmentally conscious clients and partners (Al-Hawari et al., 2021). Many organizations now seek to collaborate with IT companies that share their commitment to sustainability. This can open up new business opportunities and partnerships, further contributing to the company's long-term success and sustainability.

When followers demonstrate strong green values and sustainability, it can raise the leader's awareness of environmental issues and the importance of sustainable practices. This heightened awareness can lead to a personal commitment by the leader to integrate green principles into their leadership style and decision-making processes. If leaders find that their values align with those of their green-oriented followers, it can strengthen their commitment to sustainability (Ojo & Fauzi, 2020; Mehmood et al., 2021; Huo et al., 2021). Shared values create a sense of cohesion and unity within the organization, making it more likely for leaders to champion environmental causes and initiatives. Similarly, when followers perceive that their organization genuinely supports green initiatives and values sustainability, it can motivate and engage them more effectively. They are more likely to align their personal values with those of the organization, leading to stronger green values (Ojo & Fauzi, 2020). This alignment can be reinforced by the organization's visible commitment to environmental practices. Perceived organizational support for green values can give followers a sense of purpose and meaning in their work (Hameed et al., 2021). They are more likely to see their efforts as contributing to a larger, environmentally responsible mission, which can deepen their commitment to green values. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to explore the relationship between follower-green values and leader-green commitment within an organizational context, while also considering the moderating effect of Perceived Organizational Support (POS).

The study aims to understand how the green values exhibited by followers influence the level of commitment that leaders have toward environmentally sustainable practices and initiatives. The study intends to examine how the perception of organizational support, as perceived by both leaders and followers, may impact the relationship between follower-green values and leader-green commitment. Specifically, it seeks to determine whether high levels of POS strengthen or weaken the influence of follower green values on leader green commitment.

1. Literature Review:

Follower green values can significantly influence leader green commitment within an organization. When followers hold strong green values and prioritize environmental sustainability, it can have a positive impact on leaders' attitudes and actions toward sustainability. The divide the literature review in the following parts to comprehend the topic regarding follower green value, leader green commitment and perceived organizational support.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Resource-based theory (RBT) has been applied to the context of following green values and leader commitment to understanding how an organization's internal resources and capabilities can influence sustainability initiatives and environmental responsibility efforts. Different organizations may have varying levels of commitment to sustainability and different sets of resources dedicated to these efforts. Some organizations may invest more in green technology and innovation, while others may focus on fostering a culture of environmental responsibility (McWilliams & Siegel, 2010). The degree of uniqueness and value of these resources can influence their competitive advantage in terms of sustainability. The sustainability-related resources and capabilities within an organization should ideally be relatively immobile and difficult for competitors to replicate. For instance, a culture of environmental responsibility that aligns with follower green values and leader commitment can be challenging for competitors to mimic quickly. RBT emphasizes the importance of developing organizational capabilities, and in this context, this could involve the ability to effectively implement and manage sustainability programs, measure and report environmental performance, and adapt to changing environmental regulations and stakeholder expectations (Barney et al., 2011). Organizations that effectively leverage their resources and capabilities to align with follower green values and leader commitment are likely to gain a competitive advantage in terms of sustainability. This advantage can translate into enhanced corporate reputation, increased market share, and improved long-term financial performance.

2.2 Role of Follower green value on Leader green commitment

Followers who are passionate about environmental sustainability can inspire and influence their leaders. When leaders see that their followers value sustainability and expect responsible environmental practices, they are more likely to align their commitments with these values. If leaders and followers share similar green values, it creates a strong alignment within the organization. Leaders who personally value sustainability are more likely to integrate it into the company's mission, vision, and culture. On the other side, when followers are vocal about their green values and expectations for sustainable practices, it can put pressure on leaders to take action. Leaders feel accountable to meet these expectations and demonstrate their commitment to sustainability (Graves

& Sarkis, 2018). Followers-driven initiatives, such as sustainability committees or feedback channels, can hold leaders accountable for their commitments to environmental sustainability (Ojo & Fauzi, 2020). Leaders are more likely to follow through on their green commitments when they know they are being watched and evaluated by their followers. Therefore, we come up with following hypothesis:

H1: Follower green values has positive effect on leader green commitment

Followers with strong green values are often a source of innovative ideas for sustainable practices and improvements. Leaders can tap into this resource to develop and implement green initiatives within the organization. When followers and leaders share green values, they are more likely to collaborate effectively on sustainability projects. This collaboration can lead to more successful and impactful sustainability efforts.

2.3 Role of Perceived Organizational Support in leader-followerRelation

Perceived organizational support (POS) plays a significant role in shaping leader-follower relationships within an organization. POS refers to the extent to which employees believe that their organization values their contributions, cares about their well-being, and supports their overall work experience (Hameed et al., 2021). High POS contributes to the development of trust and respect between leaders and followers. When followers perceive that the organization values and supports them, they are more likely to trust their leaders and respect their decisions and directions. Followers with a strong sense of POS tend to be more satisfied with their jobs and committed to the organization. This job satisfaction and commitment can extend to their relationships with leaders, as they are more likely to engage positively and proactively with their work and with leadership. A positive perception of organizational support encourages open and honest communication between leaders and followers (Joo et al., 2015). Followers are more inclined to share their ideas, concerns, and feedback when they believe the organization values their input. This open communication can foster better understanding and collaboration in leader-follower relationships. Leaders who are perceived as supportive and aligned with the organization's values and culture are often seen as more effective by their followers. This perception can strengthen the leader's influence and effectiveness in guiding and leading their team. Therefore, we come up with the following hypothesis:

H2: The relationship between follower green value and leader green commitment is moderated by perceived organisation support.

The following conceptual framework has been developed:

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

2. Methodology

3.1 Sample and Procedure

The data was collected from IT companies working in Pakistan. Questionnaires were distributed among 282 respondents. The response rate is 67.34%. A convenience sampling technique was adopted to collect the data from employees of IT industry. 5-point Likert-type scales used as 1 represented "Strongly Disagree" and 5 described "Strongly Agree". The respondents consisted of 72.92% of males and 23.08% of females. Age-wise, 19.83% of the respondents range in the age group of 25-30, and 65.64% belong to the age group of 31-35. Most respondents have a master's level qualification (65.01%), and the majority of respondents fell in the experience bracket of 5-10 years (45.07) and more than 10 years (26.22%). The detailed demographic analysis is as follows:

Table 1: Demographic detail

Parameter	Classification	Percentage
Gender	Female	23.08%
	Male	72.92%
Age (Years)	25 – 30	19.83%
	31 – 35	65.64%
	35 – above	14.53%
Work Experience	Less than 1 year	4.39%
	1–5 years	24.32%
	5–10 years	45.07%
	More than 10 years	26.22%
Educational Qualification	Undergraduate	5.71%
	Graduate	29.28%
	Masters	65.01%

3.2 Measures

For measuring perceived organizational support, we took 03 items from Lamm et al., 2014 studies. These items are “I always strive to create an organization that has a positive environmental impact”, “It is concerning if our organization does not prioritize sustainable behavior for our employees”. For follower green awareness, we took 03 items from AlGhazali & Afsar, 2020. The sample items are “I always set an example for others and encourage them to take action to protect the environment”; “I always keep the environment and nature in mind in our daily behavior and decision-making”. For leader green commitment, we took 04 items from Mowday et al., 1979. The sample items are “I am proud to talk about green practices to others”; “I am willing to accept any job assignment related to green practices”.

3. Data Analysis

PLS-SEM is used that is a popular research method for analyzing complex latent variables models. It is also known as the "Holy Grail" and "silver bullet" of advanced research analysis (Cheah et al., 2018; Hair et al., 2011).

4.1 Measurement Model

The measurement model serves to showcase the validity and consistency of the various indicators or elements. To establish validity and reliability, we rely on assessments of convergent and discriminant validity, internal consistency, and indicator reliability. We evaluate instrument reliability, as well as convergent and discriminant validity, by considering metrics such as composite reliability (CR) values, average variance extracted (AVE) values, and adherence to the Fornell and Larcker Criterion.

The values of CR greater than 0.60 are acceptable; values greater than 0.70 and less than 0.95 are satisfactory (Ramayah et al., 2018). The acceptable value to achieve indicator reliability is greater than 0.7 (Ramayah et al., 2018).

To obtain the convergent validity every construct under study is required to explain at least 50% variance (AVE $> = 0.50$) by the assigned items/indicators values (Hair et al., 2017). The AVE of each construct is above 0.5.

Table 2: Measurement Model Item Loadings, Composite Reliability (CR) & Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Construct	Item	Loading	CR	AVE
Followergreen Value	FVA1	0.833	0.942	0.701
	FVA2	0.698		
	FVA3	0.864		
Leadergreen commitment	LGC1	0.778	0.955	0.701
	LGC2	0.848		
	LGC3	0.875		
	LGC4	0.879		
Perceived	POS1	0.749	0.940	0.589

Organizational support	POS2	0.706		
	POS3	0.739		

Discriminant validity was assessed following Fornell and Larcker's (1981) criterion, which stipulates that the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) on the diagonal should exceed the correlations observed on the off-diagonal.

Table 3: Discriminant validity using Fornell and Larcker's (1981) criterion.

Construct	FVA	LOC	POS
FVA	0.837		
LGC	0.82	0.837	
POS	0.184	0.229	0.768

4.2 Structural Model

The structural model showcases the relation between constructs within the research model under consideration. To assess the significance of each hypothesis, we employed the bootstrap function within Smart PLS 4.0, which generated t-statistics. This allowed us to gauge the statistical significance of each hypothesis. We used bootstrapping as it offers a robust method with bias adjustments, and it's often the preferred approach for hierarchical regression. We conducted this analysis with a total of five thousand bootstrap sub-samples to construct confidence intervals and examine both direct and indirect effects.

The statistical model moderation interaction is as follows:

Figure 2: Statistical Model

4.3 Hypothesis Testing

The results of H1 show that the beta coefficient is 0.643. The t-value of 5.656 and a p-value of 0.030 indicate the statistical significance of the beta coefficient (Table 4). The bootstrapping analysis (Table 4) indicates that the moderating effects of POS ($\beta = -0.185$, $t = 2.129$, $LLCI = -0.360$, $ULCI = -0.010$) are significant since the 95% bootstrap confidence intervals do not straddle 0 in the center. When moderation is significant, it means that the perceived organizational support is not only affecting the relationship between Follower Green values and Leader Green Commitment, but it weakens the direct relationship when POS is higher.

Table 4: Direct and Indirect effect – Hypothesis results

Relationship	Path Coefficient (β)	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	LLCI	ULCI
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Direct effect						
FGV → LGC	0.643	0.651	5.656	0.030	Supported	
Moderating effect						
FVA*POS → LGC	-0.185	0.087	2.129	0.033	-0.360	-0.010

4. Conclusion and Discussion

The aim of the present study is to investigate the moderation effect of perceived organizational support on the relationship of follower-green value and leader-green commitment. The results indicate that there is a positive relation between follower green value and leader green commitment. In other words, the data and analysis conducted in the research provide compelling evidence that followers who prioritize environmental sustainability and exhibit green values within the organization tend to find greater alignment and resonance with leaders who similarly demonstrate a high level of commitment to green and environmentally responsible practices. According to Phungula et al., 2022 study follower value has a significant impact on commitments. The finding of the present study partially concludes the Sabir & Khan, (2011) result. It explored that follower value has a positive effect on organizational culture that creates organizational commitment in others. The present study gave evidence that when followers perceive a higher level of support from their organization for green values and environmentally responsible practices, it reinforces the positive relationship between follower green values (FGV) and leader green commitment (LGC). In other words, organizational support amplifies the connection between employee green values and leader commitment to environmental sustainability.

The study also follows the “reversing the lens” perspective from leadership to followership. Shamir, 2007 suggests that there is a need to investigate from the perspective of followership. Green practices require active participation and commitment from all members of an organization. Followers, who are responsible for executing day-to-day tasks, are essential in implementing sustainability initiatives on the ground. Therefore, the present study also complies the Shamir, 2007 study by taking the followership perspective.

4.1 Theoretical implication

The study took the theoretical part from resource-based theory. The alignment of these resources (FGV, LGC, and perceived organizational support) creates a sustainable competitive advantage by enhancing the organization's ability to meet environmental goals, adapt to changing sustainability demands, and differentiate itself in the marketplace as an environmentally responsible entity. Follower Green Values (FGV) can be seen as a unique and valuable resource within an organization. Followers who genuinely embrace green values bring a distinct set of beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors that can contribute to the organization's competitive advantage in the realm of sustainability (McWilliams & Siegel, 2010). Their commitment to environmentally responsible practices can lead to increased eco-efficiency, innovation in sustainable processes, and enhanced reputation in terms of environmental stewardship. Leader Green Commitment (LGC) is another valuable resource, especially when it's aligned with FGV. Leaders who demonstrate a strong commitment to environmental sustainability not only set an example for their followers but also help to shape the organization's strategic direction and decision-making processes in favor of eco-friendly practices. Perceived organizational support (POS) can be viewed as a facilitating resource. When an organization provides support for green values and sustainability initiatives, it strengthens the connection between FGV and LGC. This support may include allocating resources for green projects, offering training and development in sustainability practices, recognizing and rewarding eco-friendly efforts, and fostering a culture that values sustainability.

5.2 Practical Implications

The IT sector has become a key driver of economic growth in Pakistan (Kazmi, 2022). It has created jobs, attracted foreign investment, and contributed to the country's GDP. This economic growth can provide resources for sustainability initiatives. The IT sector often promotes digitalization and automation, which can lead to reduced paper usage, energy efficiency, and lower carbon emissions. The growth of the IT sector can lead to increased investments in education and skills development. As more individuals acquire IT-related skills, they become better equipped to contribute to sustainability efforts through technology-driven solutions. Therefore, it is crucial to recruit those employees that value sustainability.

The study places a strong emphasis on the significance of followers within the leadership process, highlighting their pivotal role as indispensable contributors to leadership outcomes. This research asserts that active participation by followers in green practices contribute in leader green commitment. Hence, to maximize the positive impacts and address challenges, it's crucial for stakeholders, including the government, businesses, and

civil society, to collaborate on sustainable practices, energy efficiency, and digital inclusion while considering the long-term environmental and social implications.

5.3 Limitations and Future Research Directions

One common limitation in a study on the follower perspective of green practices is the sample size. Many studies may have a relatively small sample from a specific organization or industry, which limits the generalizability of the findings to a broader context. Future research should aim for larger and more diverse samples to enhance the applicability of the results. Another limitation is that this study employs cross-sectional designs, which provide a snapshot of data at a single point in time. Longitudinal or experimental designs could provide deeper insights into how follower attitudes and behaviours regarding green practices evolve over time and in response to interventions. The present study focuses on a broader aspect of green practices (e.g., recycling, energy conservation) without considering the specific spectrum of sustainability initiatives. Future research could explore how followers' perspectives vary across different types of green practices. Moreover, complements self-reported data with direct observations of follower behaviors related to green practices. This can help bridge the gap between intentions and actual actions.

Conflict of Interest:

There is no conflict of interest.

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Author Information

Tanya Munir

Ph.D. Business Studies,
Iqra University - Pakistan

Sajjad Nawaz Khan

Ph.D. Business Studies,
Iqra University - Pakistan

Adham Fayad

DBA, De Montfort University, UAE
